

Cogito: The simple intuition fallback position [Technical note]

TLDR; The fallback position does not rescue the Cogito. It merely changes the object under defense. If “ergo” is retained, the Cogito remains an argument and is subject to full inferential inspection. If “ergo” is removed, the result is no longer “Cogito ergo sum” but a weaker dual claim, closer to “cogito et sum”. If this is defended as a simple intuition, then it must still survive Descartes’ own method; otherwise it is not an indubitable foundation but simply an exempted assertion.

While ‘Appendix A: The Refutation of “Cogito ergo sum” ‘ targets and dismantles the Cogito as a coherent argument under Descartes own framework, it has been pointed out that Descartes himself (and many of his later defenders) shifted to “simple intuition” as a fallback position after his Cogito argument was criticized. It might seem superfluous, however a few observations on the fallback position seem to be in order to highlight the issues inherent in the same:

Gassendi pointed out that “cogito, ergo sum” looks like a syllogism requiring a major premise such as “whatever thinks exists.” He presses Descartes on whether this premise is known with the absolute certainty demanded by the hyperbolic doubt, or whether the Cogito smuggles in more than it claims.¹

“When someone says ‘I am thinking, therefore I am, or I exist’, he isn’t inferring existence from thought by means of a syllogism; rather, **a simple intuition of his mind** shows it to him as self-evident.

If he had been inferring it through a syllogism, it would have been this:

Everything that thinks is, or exists;
I think;
therefore I am, or exist.

And for this he would need already to have known the first premise ‘Everything that thinks is, or exists’; but what actually happens is that he learns it by experiencing in his own case that it isn’t possible to think without existing. *Constructing general propositions on the basis of our knowledge of particular ones is something that we just naturally do.*²

¹ See “Applied Homeschool Logic” in the Refutation for a complete description of the issue (Gassendi’s argument enhanced)

² Here Descartes is introducing the process of induction as a Red Herring. It is not relevant to the actual challenge posed.

Applying the principle of charity, he is then often read to the claim that the Cogito is known directly by a simple intuition of the mind, and not by a piece of reasoning³:

‘Thus, after everything has been most carefully weighed, it must finally be established that this pronouncement **“I am, I exist”** is necessarily true **every time I utter it or conceive it in my mind.**’

This seems to say “Cogito et sum” (explicitly rejects the inference), however since it is still somewhat ambiguous, it might be interpreted as the existence being dependent upon thinking occurring [Cogito ergo sum]. Unfortunately, neither Descartes nor his defenders leave it at the more reasonable “Cogito et sum” as he later silently smuggles the “ergo” back into **“ego cogito, ergo sum”** [Principles of Philosophy]. This is a structurally untenable shift; the inference is denied under pressure and later reintroduced without adequate justification. Defenders who retain ‘ergo’ while treating the Cogito as non-inferential inherit the same instability. At this point the instability is no longer hidden by Descartes’ ambiguity.

Furthermore, some seem to believe that reaching an argument by way of intuition somehow means exempting the argument from scrutiny due to the way in which it was discovered⁴. Whenever the Cogito is phrased, by Descartes or anyone else, to include therefore/donc/ergo it becomes an argument, and as shown in the refutation⁵ it does not survive Descartes own framework (hyperbolic doubt, clarity, etc.) and thus cannot be the indubitable foundation of anything whatsoever. Even if one were to forget to apply Descartes’ entire framework (and drop the claim to indubitability) the argument fails⁶ at the ergo.

Thus, one is left to consider his two claims, “I think”⁷ and “I am/exist”, from his intuition under Descartes’ framework. Now, here are two fundamental problems:

1. Once Descartes sets up his framework, under hyperbolic doubt anything dubitable must be discarded as false. Since time is dubitable⁸, it must be discarded and nothing more can happen after the framework has been established. Thus, the subsequent acts of conceiving and uttering/pronouncing become impossible ... unless time is quietly retained in breach of the framework. Descartes must thus either fall silent or cheat.
2. If that is not sufficient, his framework is self-collapsing, it cannot carry its own weight⁹.

³ In Descartes phrasing here the problematic **therefore** (donc/ergo) is missing, as would be appropriate if the claim is NOT an argument. **Note:** there is no possible reading of both the French “donc” and the Latin “ergo” that allows any other meaning other than that of indicating that what follows is the conclusion of an argument.

⁴ Intuition tends to be involved in the development of most arguments and the proofs. Descartes attempts to define his *intuition* as “that which cannot be doubted” This *intuition* seems to be special pleading to avoid hyperbolic doubt. His *intuition* is likely inspired in Aristotle’s *Nous*, but differ conveniently in not needing to provide any proof whatsoever. There cannot be any “carte blanche” obtained by use of *intuition*, especially given many thinkers have since proven that doubting his *intuitions* is not impossible, but easy.

⁵ Appendix A: The Refutation of “Cogito ergo sum”

⁶ See attack vectors: A, B, 2, 8 & 10 The argument becomes a claim to be able to think something into existence.

⁷ Utter “I am/exist” or conceive it in my mind [Presumably, the uttering is dependent upon conceiving in his mind]

⁸ See attack vector 3: Cogito ergo tempo

⁹ See attack vector 12: How can you place truth inside a structure built on extreme doubt, ...

If one suspends hyperbolic doubt before proceeding, one is still left with the problem of his other criteria of **Clarity** and **Distinctness**, where thinking fails¹⁰ to win when applied rigorously. Thus, to salvage something here we must reduce his method to simply what is self-evident¹¹.

Under what now remains of his framework, it would indeed seem self-evident that Descartes **MUST** exist in order to utter "I exist" or conceive it in his mind. What little remains of the Cogito (I must exist to think) then becomes trivially obvious, but not a foundation of knowledge.

As St Augustine succinctly put it in Enchiridion Ch VII 20:

'For no one can "not know" that he himself is alive. If he is not alive, he cannot "not know" about it or anything else at all, because either to know or to "not know" implies a living subject.'

The parallels to Descartes formulation above are evident, but St Augustine doesn't claim a **special case** for "knowing" as opposed to Descartes' "thinking". St Augustine continues:

And there are many things that are thus true and certain concerning which, if we withhold positive assent, this ought not to be regarded as a higher wisdom but actually a sort of dementia.

Thus, it seems likely that St Augustine would have approved of Monty Python's Philosopher's song:

I drink, therefore I am.

But it seems unlikely that he would have built existence upon getting drunk and thinking.

PS. Descartes takes clarity and distinctness to be the criterion for truth and certainty of perceptions/ideas (i.e. for which contents of thought can be known with absolute certainty, not just believed). It is time to apply these criteria to his description of the Cogito, and reach the inevitable conclusion. Not only does the Cogito fail, both as an argument and an intuition, but Descartes' obscurity and ambiguity indicate falsity and uncertainty ... according to Descartes himself.

¹⁰ See attack vectors 1, 6 & 7

¹¹ If not reduced, both "*I think*" and "*I am/exist*" must be proven to pass his full method despite all issues raised.